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Biology and morphometric of ber fruit fly *Carpomyia vesuviana* CostaS. M. Haldhar^{1&2}, D. K. Sarolia¹, and L. N. K. Singh²¹ICAR-Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Sri Ganganagar Highway, Beechwal Industrial Area, Bikaner (Rajasthan) 334006²College of Agriculture (CAU), Iroisemba, Imphal, Manipur 795004

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Biology, incidence and morphometric analysis of fruit fly *Carpomyia vesuviana* Costa were carried out on Indian jujube, *Ziziphus mauritiana* Lamark. The female fly laid the eggs in the cavities made by the ovipositor, just beneath the skin of the fruit. The eggs were small, elongated, spindle shaped and creamy white. The pooled mean duration of the different stages of *C. vesuviana* viz., the egg period of 1.90 days, maggot period of 8.75 days, pre-pupal period of 4.43 hours, pupal period of 8.40 days, adult longevity of 13.85 days and total life cycle of 29.95 days, respectively. The average length, width and wing expanse of female fruit fly were found to be 4.82 mm, 1.33 mm and 3.91 mm while male fruit fly was found to be 4.44 mm, 1.21 mm and 3.83 mm, respectively. The morphometric variations of different life stages of the ber fruit fly have been recorded. The incidence of fruit fly was recorded maximum in October followed by December month and minimum was recorded in the month of January in arid conditions. Correlation coefficient of incidence was significantly positive with maximum RH (0.70) and negative with maximum temperature (-0.54). Growers can adopt this study for the timely management of ber fruit fly in arid conditions.

Keywords: *Carpomyia vesuviana*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, Biology, Incidence, Morphometric analysis.

